

Extraction chromatographic studies of cadmium(II) with SRS-100, a high molecular mass carboxylic acid

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Abstract : A selective method has been developed for the extraction chromatographic separation of Cd^{II} with SRS-100 (liquid cation exchanger) coated on silanised silica gel. Quantitative extraction of Cd^{II} has been achieved from acetate buffer at the pH range 6.5–7.5. The effects of pH, stripping agents, flow-rate, on extraction and elution have been investigated. Exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger at different temperatures with respect to Cd^{II} has been determined. Cd^{II} has been separated from synthetic binary and multi-component mixtures containing various elements by exploiting the differences in pH for extraction and elution. The method effectively permits sequential separation of Cd^{II} from synthetic mixture containing its congeners Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} of same analytical group.

Keywords : SRS-100, cadmium(II), extraction.

Introduction

Relatively rare element (10⁻⁶ wt%), cadmium, in its trace level, appears to have deleterious effects on human bone (*itai-itai*)¹. Cadmium alloys are used in aircraft engines². Obviously separation of metallic toxicant, cadmium poses a challenging problem to the analytical chemists. The most widely used techniques for the separation and preconcentration of trace level Cd^{II} includes liquid-liquid extraction³, coprecipitation⁴, ion-exchange⁵, adsorption⁶, cloud point extraction⁷, electrochemical deposition⁸, extraction chromatography (EC)⁹ and solid phase extraction (SPE)¹⁰. But the systematic extraction chromatographic investigation of Cd^{II} with high molecular mass carboxylic acid (HMMCA), SRS-100 has yet not been reported. The present work reports a rapid method for the extraction chromatographic behavior of Cd^{II} with HMMCA, SRS-100 on hydrophobic silica support.

Results and discussion

The pH of the aqueous solution is an important controlling parameter in the adsorption process¹¹. The systematic extraction chromatographic studies on Cd^{II} with SRS-100 at the pH range 4.0–7.5 ensured its quantitative extraction at the optimum pH range 6.5–7.5. The complete retention of Cd^{II} at the column was found even at a flow rate of 2.5 mL min⁻¹. Common anions

like Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻ did not interfere in the extraction. Quantitative elution of Cd^{II} has been achieved with HNO₃ (0.001–0.05 M), HCl (0.001–0.05 M), NaNO₃ (0.5–1.5 M) and deionized water. Deionized water was used for the elution of Cd^{II} in the further steps of experiments.

Separation of Cd^{II} from binary mixtures : The binary separations from several metal ions were achieved either by exploiting the difference in pH for extraction or by using suitable stripping agent. When, Cd^{II}-Fe^{III} and Cd^{II}-Zr^{IV} binary mixtures were passed through the column at pH 3.0, only Cd^{II} from the mixtures was percolated through the column with the mobile phase. The extracted Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} were eluted with 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and 8 M HNO₃ respectively. Binary mixtures containing Cd^{II} with Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}, Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, In^{III}, Tl^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} when equilibrated with the exchanger at pH 5.0, except Cd^{II}, all the diverse ions were extracted at the column. After extraction, the diverse ions were eluted selectively, i.e. Cu^{II}, with 0.01 M HNO₃, Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃, Hg^{II} with 0.1 M HNO₃, Al^{III} with 0.1 M H₂SO₄, Ga^{III} with 0.5 M H₂SO₄, In^{III} with 0.2 M HNO₃, Tl^{III} with 0.2 M HNO₃, Ce^{IV} with 0.2 M H₂SO₄, Th^{IV} with 0.5 M HCl and U^{VI} with 0.02 M HNO₃. However, at pH 6.5 from the binary mixtures containing the diverse ions like Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Cr^{III}, La^{III}, Dy^{III}, Sm^{III}, Pr^{III}

and Bi^{III} except Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, all other metal ions were extracted along with Cd^{II}. In all the cases, Cd^{II} was eluted first with deionized water and then the diverse ions were eluted with selective eluents, viz. La^{III} with 0.5 M HNO₃, Dy^{III} with 0.01 M HNO₃, Sm^{III} with 0.025 M HNO₃, Pr^{III} with 0.25 M HNO₃ and Bi^{III} with 1 M HNO₃.

Separation of cadmium(II) from multi-component mixtures : In order to assess the possible analytical applications the proposed method was applied to separate

Table 1. Separation of Cd^{II} from synthetic multicomponent mixtures

Cd^{II} taken : 1.6 mg/ml; column : 0.8 × 8 cm; flow rate : 2 ml min⁻¹; pH : 3**, 5.0, 6.5*; Temp. = ~25 °C

	Metal ions	Weight added (mg)	Weight recovered (mg)	Relative error (%)	Eluent used	Eluent volume (ml)
1.	Hg ^{II}	3.4	3.4	—	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Zn ^{II}	2.0	2.0	—	—	—
	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	H ₂ O	50
2.	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	—	—
	Hg ^{II}	3.4	3.4	—	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Pb ^{II}	3.0	3.1	+3.3	1 M HNO ₃	30
3.	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	—	—
	Cu ^{II}	2.5	2.6	+4	0.02 M HNO ₃	45
	Pb ^{II}	3.0	3.1	+3.3	1 M HNO ₃	30
4.	Pb ^{II}	3.0	3.1	+3.3	1 M HNO ₃	30
	Zn ^{II}	2.0	2.0	—	—	—
	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	H ₂ O	50
5.	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	—	—
	Cu ^{II}	2.5	2.6	+4	0.02 M HNO ₃	45
	Tl ^{III}	2.0	2.1	+5	1 M HNO ₃	40
6.	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	—	—
	Hg ^{II}	3.4	3.4	—	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Tl ^{III}	2.0	2.1	+5	1 M HNO ₃	40
7.	Pb ^{II}	3.0	3.1	+3.3	1 M HNO ₃	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	H ₂ O	50
	Bi ^{III} *	2.5	2.5	—	1 M HNO ₃	20
8.	Zr ^{IV} **	2.1	2.1	—	8 M HNO ₃	25
	In ^{III}	2.4	2.4	—	0.2 M HNO ₃	100
	Cr ^{III} *	1.1	1.0	-9.1	—	—
	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	H ₂ O	50
9.	Zr ^{IV} **	2.1	2.1	—	8 M HNO ₃	25
	Ce ^{IV}	3.0	2.8	-6.7	0.2 M H ₂ SO ₄	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.6	1.6	—	—	—
	Pd ^{II}	2.9	2.9	—	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30

Cd^{II} from multi-component synthetic mixtures containing Cd^{II} with different metal ions commonly associated with it in same analytical group, ores and alloy samples. After recovery, diverse metal ions were determined complexometrically¹² and averages of five determinations were reported (Table 1). In almost all the cases fairly good reproducibility with respect to quantitative extraction and separation has been achieved.

At pH 5.0, from the ternary mixture containing Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}, only Hg^{II} was extracted at the column and was eluted with 0.1 M HNO₃. The effluent containing Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} was equilibrated at pH 6.5, when only Cd^{II} was extracted and was eluted with deionized water. At pH 5.0, from the ternary mixture of Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} only Cd^{II} was passed through the column with the mobile phase. Extracted Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} were sequentially eluted with 0.1 M HNO₃ and 1 M HNO₃ respectively. Separation of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} was achieved by passing this mixture at pH 5.0, when except Cd^{II}, both Cu^{II}, and Pb^{II} were extracted. Cu^{II} was eluted first with 0.02 M HNO₃ and Pb^{II} was eluted with 1 M HNO₃. At pH 5.0, from the ternary mixture of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}, only Pb^{II} was extracted at the column. After the elution of Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃, the effluent containing Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} was equilibrated again with the exchanger at pH 6.5 when only Cd^{II} was extracted. Cd^{II} was eluted finally with deionized water. When at pH 5.0, the ternary mixture of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Tl^{III} was equilibrated with the exchanger except Cd^{II}, both Cu^{II} and Tl^{III} were extracted at the column. Cu^{II} and Tl^{III} were eluted with 0.02 M HNO₃ and 1 M HNO₃ respectively. At pH 5.0, from the ternary mixture of Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Tl^{III} only Cd^{II} was percolated through column. Selectively Hg^{II} and Tl^{III} were eluted with 0.1 M HNO₃ and 1 M HNO₃ respectively. From the ternary mixture of Cd^{II}, Pb^{II} and Bi^{III} except Pb^{II} both Cd^{II} and Bi^{III} were passed through the column at pH 5.0. Extracted Pb^{II} was eluted with 1 M HNO₃. Effluent containing Cd^{II} and Bi^{III} was equilibrated again at pH 6.5, when both of them were extracted. Elution of Cd^{II} and Bi^{III} were made by deionized water and 1 M HNO₃ respectively. From the quaternary mixture of Cd^{II}, Cr^{III}, In^{III} and Zr^{IV} at pH 3.0 only Zr^{IV} was extracted at the column and was eluted with 8 M HNO₃. Effluent containing all the rest metals was passed through the column at pH 5.0, when only In^{III} was extracted. After the elution of In^{III} with 0.2 M HNO₃, the effluent was again equilibrated with the exchanger at pH 6.5 when only Cd^{II} was extracted and Cr^{III} was passed through the column. Cd^{II} was eluted with deionized

water. Separation of Cd^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ce^{IV} and Zr^{IV} was achieved by passing the multicomponent mixture at pH 3.0, when only Zr^{IV} was extracted and it was eluted with 8 M HNO₃. The effluent containing Cd^{II}, Pd^{II} and Ce^{IV} was passed through column at pH 5.0, when only Ce^{IV} was extracted and was eluted with 0.2 M H₂SO₄. Effluent of pH 5.0 contains Pd^{II} and Cd^{II}. This effluent was passed through the column at pH 6.5, when both the metal ions were extracted. Cd^{II} was eluted first with deionized water and then Pd^{II} was eluted with 0.2 M NH₄SCN.

Experimental

Digital Elico LI-120 pH meter combined with glass electrode, a 7D-1F thermostat, chromatographic glass column (0.8 × 8 cm) were used. A liquid cation exchanger, SRS-100 (Shell Chemical, London, England), a high molecular mass synthetic C₁₅-C₁₆ mono carboxylic acid, was used without any further purification. A standard stock solution of Cd^{II} (1.6 mg mL⁻¹) estimated complexometrically¹². Buffer solutions of different pHs were prepared from acetic acid (0.2 M) and ammonium acetate (0.2 M) in proper ratio.

Preparation of ion exchange material : Silica gel (60–120 mesh) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to vapour of dimethyldichlorosilane (DMDCS) in N₂ atmosphere. The DMDCS treated (silanised) silica gel was then washed with anhydrous methanol and dried at 100 °C. The silanised silica gel was impregnated with SRS-100, diluted in benzene and was dried in a rotary vacuum evaporator to achieve uniform coating¹³. Excess benzene was washed with 2 M HCl. Each column could be used for at least 50 cycles without any loss of its exchange capacity.

Exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger (1.65 meq of H⁺/g at 25 °C) was determined at different temperatures by measuring the milliequivalent of sodium ions absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in H⁺ form¹⁴.

Extraction procedure : Ion exchanger was loaded in

the chromatographic column and the pH of the exchanger bed was adjusted to the desired value with acetate buffer (0.2 M). An aliquot containing 1.6 mg/ml of Cd^{II} in acetate buffer was passed through the column at a flow rate of 2.0 mL min⁻¹ at ~25 °C. After extraction, Cd^{II} was stripped with deionised water, and the amount of Cd^{II} from each fraction was determined complexometrically.

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